

Alkylation of Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanones.

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In a system containing a conjugated double bond of the type $O=\overset{1}{C}-\overset{2}{C}=\overset{3}{CR}$, the ethylenic linkage is generally found to be more reactive than the carbonyl (Harries and Lellmann, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 230, 2726; Harries and Jablonski, *Ber.*, 1898, 30, 1370; Vorländer, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 2053; *Annalen*, 1897, 294, 273; Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1214; Knoevenagel, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4464). On condensing hydroxymethylene cyclohexanones with cyanacetamide, quinoline derivatives are obtained (Sen Gupta, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1347). From this the conclusion is drawn that the methylene group of cyanacetamide is more reactive towards the ethylenic than the ketonic bond of the hydroxymethylene ketone, the reaction being supposed to take place in the following way:

The suggestion that quinoline and not *iso*quinoline derivatives are to be expected owing to the aldehydic nature of hydroxymethylene cycloketones, does not appear to be probable as the reactivity of a β -diketone with cyanacetamide tends to disappear where the chance of enolisation is small (Sen and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 51) and that identical quinoline derivatives are obtained from hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone and its acetate—

Our original idea was to prepare the *O*-alkyl ethers of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanones.

and condense them with cyanacetamide with a view to obtain quinoline derivatives, and thus adduce fresh evidence in support of the original hypothesis.

The alkyl ethers are usually formed by the action of alkyl iodides on the sodium salt of hydroxymethylene compounds

Claisen prepared the ethyl ether of hydroxymethylene camphor in this manner (*Chem. Centr.*, 1890, ii, 878). The ethers undergo hydrolysis and regenerate original ketones, rupture taking place at the double bond.

Contrary to our expectation, it was found that the reaction did not proceed in this manner with hydroxymethylenecyclohexanones. For, when alkyl iodides were allowed to react with their sodium salts, the products on hydrolysis did not yield the original ketones from which the hydroxymethylene compounds were derived, but instead, new ketones were obtained in which alkyl substitution in the *ortho*-position to the ketonic group had taken place. As these ketones were often unmixed with the original ketones, it could be held that *O*-alkyl ethers were not being generally formed. Evidently the products were mainly *C*-alkyl ethers which alone could give alkylated ketones on hydrolysis of the formyl group.

That the first product formed by the interaction of the Na-salt of hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone with an alkyl iodide is a substituted keto-aldehyde is shown by the reduction of ammoniacal silver nitrate and copper salt solutions. This behaviour of the

hydroxymethylene compound is very different from the ordinary and can be explained by assuming :

(I) The wandering of an alkyl group from oxygen to carbon after the formation of the *O*-ether.

(II) An addition reaction followed by separation of sodium iodide such as Michael assumes in explaining the formation of *C*-derivatives from the sodium compound of acetoacetic ester and alkyl iodides (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1888, (ii)37, 478).

(III) By assuming an aldehydic structure for the sodium compound when direct substitution of Na by an alkyl group takes place.

Assumption (I) does not appear to be probable. The formation of the *C*-compound takes place even in the cold and without the use of a reagent which is known to produce isomeric change under

the condition. Similar *O*-alkyl compounds like the ethyl ether of hydroxymethylenecamphor do not appear to be so unstable. Again such an assumption does not find favour in explaining the formation of *C*-derivatives of acetoacetic ester. Regarding (II) it may be seen that it does not satisfactorily explain the two different types of reactions as represented by the formation of *O*-ethers in certain cases and *C*-derivatives in others. If it is assumed that addition reactions take place in the latter and substitution in the former and that the nature of the reaction (addition or substitution) is determined by Michael's negative positive rule, it cannot be imagined why any difference should be observed, for instance, between hydroxymethylenecamphor and hydroxymethylene*ortho*-methylcyclohexanone both of which possess similar structures but yield different kinds of alkyl compounds.

Hydroxymethylene camphor.

Hydroxymethylene-*o*-methyl-
cyclohexanone.

As regards (III) there is admittedly a great difficulty in giving an aldehydic structure to the sodium salt, as, in the first place, hydroxymethylene ketones have generally been regarded as pure enolic compounds (Claisen, *Chem. Centr.*, 1890, (ii), 878; von Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 1040). Claisen, in fact, distinguishes them from β -diketones, as, according to him, only *O*-derivatives can be obtained from the sodium compounds of the former (which is however not a fact as seen in the present case) whereas those of the latter can give *C*-derivatives (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 1776). The existence of the aldehydo form in the free hydroxymethylene compound, which must be a condition that the aldehydic sodium compound may exist, does not appear to have been established before. W. Wislicenus considered α and β forms of the methyl and ethyl esters of formyl phenyl acetic acid (other forms obtained he regarded as mixtures) as keto and enol modifications at first but after reviewing all evidence for thirty years he is now inclined to the belief that they are *cis*- and *trans*-enol forms both of which rapidly absorb a molecule of bromine and are

equally soluble in alkali solution (*Annalen*, 1896, **291**, 147; 1900, **312**, 62; 1912, **389**, 270; 1916, **413**, 206; *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 2837; Michael, *Annalen*, 1912, **391**, 235, 215; 1914, **406**, 137; Meyer, *Ber.*, 1912, **46**, 2868; Dieckmann, *Ber.*, 1916, **49**, 2213). Dieckmann also holds the same view (*Ber.*, 1917, **50**, 1357). Recent absorption spectra method supports the same conclusion (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **131**, 713). K. H. Meyer's bromine titration method, applied to few hydroxymethylene ketones by some investigators, shows them to be enolic compounds.

As no alternative to (III) could be thought of, it was necessary to determine whether the hydroxymethylene compounds under investigation were really pure enols or mixtures of *keto* and *enol* phases. The matter was settled by directly determining the percentage of enol in them. Applying Meyer's method some were found to contain a fairly large porportion of the *keto* form. Hydroxymethylene*ortho*methylcyclohexanone, for example, contains about 54% and hydroxymethylene-*meta*-methylcyclohexanone about 40% of the *keto* form. Their behaviour was also found to be exactly analogous to the other class of substances which show *keto-enol* tautomerism, so far as the effect of solvent, temperature and concentration on the equilibrium is concerned.

It has been determined by different observers both by chemical and physical methods that dissociating solvents like alcohol rapidly ketonises the enol and, whereas the equilibrium is shifted towards the *keto* side in such media, it is shifted towards the enol in solvents like benzene and that dilution in the same solvent always increases the proportion of the enol form (Wislicenus, *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 2837; Bruhl, *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 2326; K. H. Meyer, *Annalen*, 1911, **380**, 212; *Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 3044).

Hantzsch (*loc. cit.*), by absorption spectra method, finds that the equilibrium is shifted towards the enol side by the rise of temperature. Meyer on the other hand, after studying a number of compounds, concludes that the *keto* form is favoured by the rise of temperature (*Annalen*, 1911, **380**, 212; *Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 833).

The rapid ketonising effect of alcoholic solution was observed in all the cases we have examined (*vide* Experimental). Similar effect has been noticed by Meyer in the case of ethyl acetoacetate (*Annalen*, 1911, **380**, 212).

The enolising effect of benzene and more so of ether was observed with hydroxymethylene-*p*-methylcyclohexanone. Alcohol, ether

and benzene as solvents all showed approximately 77 per cent. of enol on the first day. After a week 50 per cent. of enol was observed in alcoholic solution whereas the enolic value rose to 93 per cent. in benzene and 97 per cent. in ether. Meyer, with acetoacetic ester, finds a higher percentage of enol in ether than in benzene (*Annalen*, 1911, 380, 212) but the observation of Wislicenus appears to be in the opposite direction. Regarding the effect of concentration, dilution was noticed to show increased enolic percentage though the effect was not much marked. A 0.47 per cent. solution of hydroxymethylene-*p*-methylcyclohexanone in alcohol showed 87 per cent. of enol, whilst an 1.32 per cent. solution in the same solvent showed only 80 per cent. of enol after the same interval from the time of preparing the solutions. Hydroxymethylenecamphor practically contains 100 per cent. of enol. Other compounds examined showed similar results (*vide* Experimental).

These results leave no doubt as to the possibility of the existence of the keto form in the hydroxymethylene compound and consequently of the aldehydic sodium compound. Nef's assumption that sodium in carbonyl compounds is never directly attached to carbon is disproved (Brühl, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 366). Though an enolic formula is usually given to the sodium compound of tautomeric substances, the most satisfactory explanation as suiting the most varied condition is that supplied by Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 1508) in which there is an equilibrium established between the dissociated ions of the two metallic derivatives or in other words, an equilibrium mixture of both metallic compounds is present. The equilibrium of the sodium compound of acetoacetic ester is represented as

which is equivalent to the presence of two sodium compounds $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}(\text{ONa}) : \text{CHCOOC}_2\text{H}_5$ and $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{CHNa} \cdot \text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$. The equilibrium may shift from the one side to the other according to the conditions of the reaction or nature of the reagent or both. In our case, it may be assumed that the alkyl iodide reacts with the sodium compound of one form only, either the enolic or the aldehydic, both of which exist in equilibrium. The exclusive formation of one kind can be easily explained.

It may be mentioned in this connection that the action of acetyl chloride and benzoyl chloride proceeds in these cases in the usual way, *i.e.*, the acetates and benzoates of the following formulae are

formed by simple substitution of the enolic sodium compound. This is in accordance with Lapworth's view. The conception of equilibrium between metallic derivatives therefore finds an important confirmation in the above reactions which can then be satisfactorily explained on the simple substitution principle.

As already mentioned, the *C*-alkyl ethers undergo hydrolysis and alkylated ketones result. The reaction is found to be general with cyclohexanone and the different substituted cyclohexanones if only one *ortho*-position is free to yield hydroxymethylene derivatives. Indeed, the method can be used for general synthetical preparations of *ortho*-alkylated ketones. By using sodium salts and different alkyl iodides, methyl, ethyl, isopropyl and benzyl radicals have been introduced into the nuclei of different cyclo-ketones in *ortho*-position to the ketonic group. Thus cyclohexanone gives a mono-substituted, and mono- and di-alkyl ketones give di- and tri-alkyl ketones respectively. The mono alkyl compounds obtained from hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone in alcoholic solution, sodium ethoxide and an alkyl iodide or from the sodium salt in benzene or ether suspension and an alkyl iodide, are pure and obtained in good yield.

The dialkyl compounds obtained from mono-alkyl ketones is obtained as mixtures of the two in alcoholic solution which can however be separated ; but pure products may be obtained by using the dry sodium salt in ether or benzene suspension. The reaction product may be easily identified on the following basis :

On distilling the alkylated product with alkali solution, any free hydroxymethyleneketone or its *O*-derivative yields the original ketone and the *ortho*-alkyl derivatives. Thus the hydrolysed product in all cases will be either the original ketone, or the substituted ketone, or a mixture of the two. Instances of all these have been noticed in carrying out the reaction in alcoholic solution. cycloHexanone in this way produces pure *o*-methylcyclohexanone, the three methyl compounds give mixtures, whereas the original ketone is obtained

when acetophenone is used, an *O*-alkyl compound being the only methylation product in the last case. The products can be mostly identified by comparison with the known ketones specially in the form of their derivatives (oximes or semicarbazones).

When the sodium salt of hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone is heated with methyl iodide in dry benzene, a thick oil is obtained which distils with decomposition. The liquid reduces alkaline copper and silver salt solutions and does not form a semicarbazone easily which it readily yields on addition of dilute caustic soda solution or on distilling with it. The semicarbazone melts at 192° which shows no lowering when mixed with the semicarbazone prepared from a sample of pure *o*-methylcyclohexanone. The hydrolysed liquid itself has the characteristic smell of *o*-methylcyclohexanone and has the same boiling point. The reaction may be represented as follows:

It is interesting to note that when hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone is heated with sodium ethoxide and methyl iodide in alcoholic solution in a pressure bottle, the entire product is at once *ortho*-methylcyclohexanone. We may assume that the *C*-methyl ether which is first formed, is decomposed by alcoholic alkali to *O*-methyl cyclohexanone.

On the other hand, carrying on this reaction under reflux, two fractions are obtained. The lower fraction is *o*-methylcyclohexanone and the higher fraction on removal of the little free hydroxy-

methylene cyclohexanone it contains, yields *o*-methylcyclohexanone on treatment with dilute caustic soda solution. The higher fraction probably contains the undecomposed *C*-methyl ether as the proportion of the lower fraction increases and that of the higher decreases on longer heating. Pure *o*-methylcyclohexanone is also obtained from the Na-salt taken in ether and treated in the cold with methyl iodide. Thus it appears, the sodium salt could not be made to produce any *O*-methyl ether under any of the conditions mentioned which, if produced, must have been in very small quantities, as, otherwise, it would have contaminated the final product with cyclohexanone. There is reason to believe, however, that such alkylations do not always proceed to completion depending on the solvent and the temperature used, accounting thereby for the comparatively lower yields of synthesised alkyl ketones.

An attempt was made to bring about the condensation of the *C*-methyl ether with cyanacetamide as it would throw some light on the question whether the condensation of the latter substance with free hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone was taking place in its enolic or aldehydic phase. If the latter, the β -keto-aldehyde used would give rise to a quinoline derivative, thus :

But as no condensation (Michael or Knoevenagel) occurred, one would be inclined to think that condensation of the hydroxymethylene ketone occurs in its enolic phase. Sen and Basu similarly failed to obtain any condensation product from methyl acetyl cyclohexanone

and cyanacetamide (*loc. cit*) There also the difficulty of enolisation probably hindered condensation.

But the fact that the formyl group of the *C*-methyl ether is readily split off must not be lost sight of. The compound might

have got decomposed before any condensation with cyanacetamide could occur.

It has already been mentioned that each of the *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-methyl cyclohexanones gives a dimethyl ketone.

2: 6-Dimethyl
from *ortho*.

2: 5-Dimethyl
from *meta*.

2: 4 Dimethyl
from *para*.

Whereas the product is a pure dimethyl ketone when ether or benzene is used with the sodium salt, hydroxymethylene mono methyl ketone in alcoholic solution in the presence of sodium ethoxide produces a mixture of a mono- and a di-methyl ketone, the latter however being invariably in excess of the other. It appears, therefore, that the possibility of *O*-alkyl ethers or the hydroxymethylene ketone itself being hydrolysed to the original ketone cannot be altogether ignored. The case of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone itself is different from other homologues, as the former yields alkylated ketone whether in ether, benzene, or alcoholic medium, whereas the latter namely homologues of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone give a mixture of alkylated ketone and the original ketone in alcoholic solution.

From the feregoing reactions as also from the analogy which the hydroxymethylene ketones are found to bear to acetyl cycloketones it could be seen that menthone could be synthesised from hydroxymethylene-*m*-methylcyclohexanone and isopropyl iodide after the manner of its production from 2-acetyl-5-methylcyclohexanone in presence of sodium ethoxide.

It would also be expected from what has already been noticed that in alcoholic solution, a mixture of *m*-methyl*cyclo*hexanone and menthone would be obtained. The expectation was justified by the results obtained. The hydrolysed product was a liquid from which the smell of menthone could be perceived. The semicarbazone obtained from this liquid was impure and repeated crystallisation gave no pure product but the oxime prepared from the mixture which melted at 78°, on crystallising once from alcohol, melted at 83° and on second crystallisation from the same solvent, melted fairly sharp at 92°. The oxime thus obtained was shining crystals but the yield was small. The melting point of the oxime of inactive menthone is differently given as 78-82° and 98-99°.

That the reaction of the sodium salt of the hydroxymethylene ketone with acetyl chloride did not produce a *C*-derivative (I) or (II) after the following fashion :

but an acetate of the following formula

appeared from the following considerations. The thick liquid that was obtained by ether extraction after treating the sodium salt of hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone in ether suspension with acetyl chloride was treated with dilute alkali. If the first reaction took

place, acetyl *cyclohexanone* was most likely to be obtained after the last operation. But the liquid was not found to possess the properties of the latter. The thick liquid had the acetate-like smell quite unlike that of acetyl *cyclohexanone*. Besides it did not give any immediate colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. Acetyl *cyclohexanone* (a β -diketone) at once develops violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. The slow appearance of colour in the acetylated compound, which also appeared on warming, may be attributed to hydrolysis and change into the hydroxymethylene ketone. The formula for the acetate was confirmed by analysis of the semicarbazone which was quickly formed from the liquid. Mention has already been made of this acetate which was obtained by the action of acetic anhydride on hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* and its condensation with cyanacetamide. The action of benzoyl chloride is similar to the above. By the same series of arguments the solids prepared are proved to be benzoates which like the acetates readily form semicarbazones and appear to give quinoline condensation products with cyanacetamide. The smell of ethyl benzoate is distinctly perceptible when the benzoate and cyanacetamide are treated with sodium ethoxide in alcoholic solution. The condensation product may be supposed to be formed according to the following scheme:—

The Na-salt of hydroxymethylene acetophenone does not give anything like propiophenone with methyl iodide or butyrophenone with ethyl iodide. Its reaction appears to be similar to that of the sodium compound of hydroxymethylene camphor though one is an open-chain ketone and the other a cyclic compound. Liquid products which are obtained rapidly absorb bromine and yield pure aceto-

phenone on hydrolysis. They are, therefore, *O*-ethers. Ethoxy methylene acetophenone gave a condensation product with cyanacetamide which melted above 280°. The yield being small, the nature of the reaction could not be investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Methyl Iodide on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene-cyclohexanone in Benzene Suspension.

To hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone (20 g.) in 150 c.c. of dry benzene the requisite quantity of metallic sodium (wire) was added. The mixture was heated on the water-bath at 100° when the metal began slowly to react as indicated by the evolution of hydrogen. The superficial incrustation of the sodium salt was broken up from time to time to expose fresh surface and the heating was continued for 18 hours. The sodium salt thus obtained was a bulky granular powder. It was introduced together with benzene into a pressure bottle and heated for 12 hours at 100° with three times the required quantity of methyl iodide. After cooling, the precipitate of sodium iodide was filtered off and the benzene solution of the reaction product distilled under ordinary pressure to get rid of benzene. The residual liquid was distilled under reduced pressure, when it distilled with slight decomposition. At 130-150°/45 mm. a coloured distillate (10 g.) was obtained. This liquid reduced Fehling's solution (when heated with or without the addition of alcohol) or ammoniacal silver nitrate. The liquid however did not readily form a semicarbazone which however at once appeared on the addition of dilute caustic soda solution. This semicarbazone was found to be identical with that of *o*-methylcyclohexanone (m.p. 191°-92°).

Hydrolysis of the above Liquid: Formation of 2-Methylcyclohexanone.

The liquid was distilled with dilute caustic soda solution. The distillate was extracted with ether. It had the characteristic smell of *o*-methylcyclohexanone, and gave a semicarbazone which appeared as shining crystals from alcohol. The semicarbazone melted at 192°. It showed no lowering of m.p. when it was mixed

with the semicarbazone of *o*-methylcyclohexanone which latter also melted at 192°. (Found: N, 25.01. $C_8H_{15}ON_3$ requires N, 24.85 per cent.).

Action of Methyl Iodide on Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone in Alcoholic Solution in Presence of Sodium Ethoxide under Pressure.

Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone (25 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (70 c.c.), sodium (4.6 g. dissolved in 100 c.c. of alcohol) was added to it. The solution which contained the sodium salt of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone was heated on the water-bath with about three times the requisite amount of methyl iodide (70 g.) in a pressure bottle till neutral (6 hours). The excess of methyl iodide and alcohol were distilled off from sand-bath and water was added to the residue and its ether extract taken. It was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and on expelling the ether from water-bath, the residual liquid was distilled under reduced pressure (yield, 14 g.); b.p. 86°-88°/49 mm. The liquid boiled at 164-166° under ordinary pressure. The semicarbazone prepared from the liquid came down in beautiful crystals, m. p. 189°. A mixture of this semicarbazone with that of *o*-methylcyclohexanone showed no lowering. The semicarbazone was obtained in still purer condition melting at 192° by removing the traces of contaminating free hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone from the liquid by washing it with dilute alkali solution and finally distilling it with the same. Apart from the smell of the liquid which is sufficient to characterise it as *o*-methylcyclohexanone, the comparison of the semicarbazone with that of a known sample of *o*-methylcyclohexanone and the analysis of the semicarbazone, established the liquid to be *o*-methylcyclohexanone.

The above Experiment carried out under Reflux.

On conducting the experiment under reflux two fractions were obtained. The lower fraction (10 g.) boiled at 93-98°/ 52 mm. which was identified as *o*-methylcyclohexanone containing a small amount of unaltered the hydroxymethylene compound. The higher fraction collected between 110° and 130° was redistilled but no steady boiling point was obtained. The hydroxymethylene ketone was removed from the liquid by treatment with dilute sodium carbonate solution as the soluble sodium salt. The liquid was distilled with dilute

caustic soda solution and the distillate was pure *o*-methylcyclohexanone as was shown by its semicarbazone.

Action of Methyl Iodide on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone in Ether Suspension in the Cold.

Ten gms. of the sodium salt thoroughly washed with dry ether were mixed with an excess of methiodide in a closed vessel which was shaken from time to time. After about a week the contents were filtered and the ether was removed in vacuum. Two gms. of a liquid were obtained which gave *o*-methyl-cyclohexanone on treatment with dilute NaOH solution. It was considered pure as its semicarbazone melted sharp at 192°.

Action of Ethyl Iodide on Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone.

Ten gms. of a colourless liquid were obtained from 20 gms. of hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone when the latter was heated with the required amount of sodium ethoxide, alcohol and ethyl iodide. The liquid distilled at 125-135°/10 mm. On a second distillation, a fraction was collected which boiled at 120-132°/10 mm. After treating it in the usual way to remove hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone, the presence of which was detected by the ferric chloride reaction, and hydrolysing the liquid, a semicarbazone was prepared. It was crystallised from alcohol; m. p. 157°. The semicarbazone of ethyl cyclohexanone is known to melt at 157°. (Found: N, 23.1. C₉H₁₇ON₃ requires N, 22.9 per cent.).

*Action of Methyl Iodide on Hydroxymethylene-*o*-methyl cyclohexanone.*

Conducting the experiment in alcoholic solution in presence of sodium ethoxide in a closed bottle and proceeding as before 15 gms. of a liquid having peppermint-like odour were collected (using 25 gms. of the hydroxymethylene compound). The liquid distilled at 170-200° under ordinary pressure but the greater portion of it boiled at 175-180°. The whole of the liquid was distilled with 20% caustic soda solution. The oil was extracted from the distillate with ether. The semicarbazone prepared from the colourless liquid melted completely at 183°. It was impure and analysis showed about 24% of nitrogen. As the semicarbazone of the monomethyl ketone contains 25% nitrogen and that of the dimethyl ketone 23%, the liquid appeared to be a mixture of nearly equal quantities of *o*-methylcyclohexanone and the dimethyl compound derived from

it. An oxime was prepared from it by the following method. Three gms. of the liquid were dissolved in methyl alcohol. A slight excess of hydroxylamine hydrochloride with four times the theoretical amount of caustic soda solution was added to the solution and heated for half an hour on the water-bath. The whole was allowed to evaporate spontaneously in air when the oxime crystallised out slowly. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol it melted at 118° . This corresponded to the oxime of 2:6-dimethylcyclohexanone. (Found: N, 10.35. $C_8H_{15}ON$ requires N, 10.0 per cent.).

By conducting the methylation under reflux and in alcoholic solution, 16 gms. of 2-methyl hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone gave 16 gms. of the methylated product boiling at 110-150/40 mm. On fractionation, two equal fractions were collected—one boiling at 120-130/30 mm. and the other at 130-135/30 mm. On hydrolysing both fractions with 20% NaOH, and treating the steam distilled product with hydroxylamine, an oxime melting at 118° was obtained. This corresponded to the oxime of 2:6-dimethylcyclohexanone.

Action of Methyl Iodide on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene o-methylcyclohexanone in Benzene Suspension.

A small yield of the dimethyl compound was obtained in a manner described in the first experiment. That the dimethyl compound was formed appeared from the peppermint-like odour of the liquid which is distinct from that of o-methylcyclohexanone. That the liquid was a very nearly pure dimethyl ketone was proved by preparing its semicarbazone which formed fine crystals (from alcohol) and melted at $193-194^{\circ}$. The mixture of this semicarbazone with that of o-methylcyclohexanone melted at 178° . (Found: N, 23.4. $C_9H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 23.00 per cent.).

Action of Methyl Iodide on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene-m-methylcyclohexanone.

The sodium salt of hydroxymethylene m-methylcyclohexanone was suspended in ether and was kept at room temperature in contact with methyl iodide. After several days, the dimethyl compound having the smell of the above dimethyl ketone was obtained by hydrolysing the resultant liquid. Its semicarbazone melted at 176° . The semicarbazone of 2:5-dimethylcyclohexanone is known to melt at 176° .

A mixture of this semicarbazone with that of *m*-methyl-cyclohexanone melted at 150-155°. The semicarbazone was pure. (Found: N, 23.25. $C_9H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 23 per cent.).

Action of Methyl Iodide on Hydroxymethylene-p-methylcyclohexanone in Alcoholic Solution with Methyl Iodide and Sodium Ethoxide.

Proceeding in the usual way, an impure product having the same peppermint-like odour of the other two dimethyl ketones was obtained. The liquid (in alcohol) quickly gave an oxime when shaken with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and excess of concentrated caustic soda solution. On crystallising from alcohol the oxime came out in long colourless prismatic needles which melted at 96°. (Found: N, 10.01. $C_8H_{15}ON$ requires N, 10.0 per cent.).

Analysis of the semicarbazone prepared showed the methylated product to be a mixture of the mono- and the di-methyl ketone. (Found: N, 23.96. $C_9H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 23 per cent.).

Action of Benzyl Iodide on Hydroxymethylene-o-methylcyclohexanone.—2-Methyl-6-benzylcyclohexanone was prepared from hydroxymethylene-o-methylcyclohexanone and benzyl iodide using alcohol and sodium ethoxide. The yield was small and the semicarbazone was impure. It melted at 140° sintering at 132°.

Menthone.—Hydroxymethylene-*m*-methylcyclohexanone (20 gms.) with isopropyl iodide (55 g.) and the requisite amount of sodium dissolved in alcohol were heated in a closed bottle for 6 hours. A colourless liquid (13 g.) distilling at 107-115°/40 mm. was collected and distilled with caustic soda solution. Menthone-like smell could be recognised in the distillate but the odour was not distinct as it was masked to a great extent by that of *m*-methyl-cyclohexanone which could also be perceived. The oxime which was prepared from the liquid by the previous method melted at 73-78°. By crystallising it from alcohol the colourless oxime melted at 80-83°. After a second crystallisation from alcohol, fine colourless shining crystals that were obtained melted fairly sharp at 92°. Analysis showed a little higher percentage of N. Exactly similar result was obtained by repeating the experiment. (Found: N, 8.8. $C_{10}H_{20}ON$ requires N, 8.3 per cent.).

The semicarbazone after crystallising once from alcohol melted completely at 120°, after another crystallisation at 128°. After

two more crystallisations, the m.p. rose to 145° but no pure product was obtained. This was analysed and from the percentage of N it contained, it was concluded that the hydrolysed liquid was a mixture of the two ketones which could only be present in the final product. (Found: N, 22.76. $C_{11}H_{21}ON_3$ requires N, 20.1 per cent. $C_8H_{15}ON_3$ requires N, 24.90 per cent.).

Action of Methyl Iodide on Hydroxymethylene-3:4-dimethyl cyclohexanone.

From the sodium salt and methyl iodide, 2:3:4-trimethyl-cyclohexanone was obtained. Its semicarbazone melted at 212°. A mixture of this semicarbazone with that of the dimethyl ketone used for its preparation sintered at 190° and melted completely at 200°. The trimethyl ketone has the same smell as the dimethyl ketone. The semicarbazone of the dimethyl ketone melts at 190°. (Found: N, 21.5. $C_{11}H_{19}ON_3$ requires N, 21.35 per cent.).

Action of Acetyl Chloride on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone.

Ten gms. of sodium salt were suspended in ether and an excess of acetyl chloride was gradually added to the sodium salt while it was kept cool in ice. Sodium chloride separated with stirring of the mixture. The product was extracted with ether and treated with dilute sodium carbonate solution. The viscous oil which was obtained from it was almost colourless, possessed the smell of an acetate and only slowly gave colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. It readily formed a semicarbazone which was crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 182-184°. A mixture of this with the semicarbazone of cyclohexanone melted at 155°. The liquid readily absorbed bromine and on hydrolysis yielded cyclohexanone, the semicarbazone of which melted at 166°. (Found: N, 19.01. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3N_3$ requires N, 18.75 per cent.).

Action of Acetyl Chloride on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene-m-methylcyclohexanone.—The acetate was obtained as in the previous experiment in the form of a viscous oil. It had all the properties of the above acetate but did not readily form a semicarbazone.

Action of Benzoyl Chloride on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene-o-methylcyclohexanone.—To 50 gms. of the sodium salt of hydroxymethylene-o-methyl-cyclohexanone in ether suspension, benzoyl chloride was gradually added. The mixture became

hot while sodium chloride separated. After the reaction was complete, which could be easily tested with FeCl_3 , the mixture was treated with very dilute caustic soda solution. On extracting the mixture with ether and evaporating the ether, 10 gms. of a solid were obtained. This was crystallised from alcohol and melted at 85° . It is unstable and decomposes on keeping for several days. Its alcoholic solution does not give coloration with ferric chloride. The colour however appears on standing. It readily gave a semicarbazone, m. p. 175° . (Found: N, 14.2. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 13.95 per cent.).

Action of Benzoyl Chloride on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene-p-methylcyclohexanone.—Proceeding as above, a solid benzoate was obtained which melted at 95° . It had all the properties of the other benzoate. Its semicarbazone melted at $183\text{--}184^\circ$. (Found: N, 14.2. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_3\text{N}_3$ requires N, 13.95 per cent.).

Action of Methyl Iodide on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene acetophenone.—The sodium salt of hydroxymethylene acetophenone (35 g.) was heated with methyl iodide and benzene for 12 hours. On removing benzene, a coloured liquid (8 gms.) with peculiar smell boiling at $120\text{--}130^\circ/45$ m.m. was obtained which could not be obtained pure, as it decomposed on heating. The liquid readily absorbed bromine, did not form a semicarbazone quickly and on hydrolysis, yielded pure acetophenone. The semicarbazone of the hydrolysed product melted at $196\text{--}197^\circ$. Acetophenone semicarbazone also melted at the same temperature. A mixture of the two melted at 196° . The experiment was carried out in presence of alcohol when only acetophenone was obtained on hydrolysis. (Found: N, 23.6. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_3$ requires N, 23.7 per cent.).

Action of Ethyl Iodide on the Sodium Salt of Hydroxymethylene acetophenone.—The small quantity of a coloured liquid which was obtained by heating the sodium salt with ethyl iodide alone was found to yield acetophenone on hydrolysis. It gave a condensation product with cyanacetamide in presence of piperidine which melted with decomposition above 230° . It dissolved in caustic soda solution on warming. The yield was small.

Estimation of the Keto-Enol Quantities in the Hydroxymethylene Ketones.

Hydroxymethylene-m-methylcyclohexanone.—2.3575 Gms. of the pure compound were dissolved in 250 c.c. of alcohol. Freshly

prepared bromine solution in alcohol (N/10) was added to 10 c.c. of the above solution in slight excess so that the colour of bromine persisted in the liquid. The temperature was kept at -7° during the addition of bromine. β -Naphthol also dissolved in alcohol was immediately added in order to remove the uncombined bromine. On the addition of potassium iodide solution, iodine was liberated. After warming for a minute the liberated iodine was titrated with standard thiosulphate solution. The following results were obtained:

	1st day.	After 12 days.	After 4 months.
P.c. of enol.....	62	41	13

Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone:—1.0865 Gm. of the substance were dissolved in 250 c.c. of alcohol. The following results were obtained.

	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.	7th day.	After 8 days.
P.c. of enol	87	77	67	66	66	66.5	66	67

On boiling with alcohol for 3 minutes—45% enol.

Hydroxymethylene-p-methylcyclohexanone.
(In Alcohol).

1.1730 Gms. of the substance dissolved in 250 c.c. of alcohol gave the following results.

	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	7th day.	After 18 days.	After 3 months.
P.c. of enol...	87	80	68	50	40	20

(In Benzene).

1.0940 Gms. dissolved in 250 c.c. of benzene showed the following results.

	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	6th day.	After 7 days.
P.c. of enol...85	86	93	93	93	93.5

(In Ether).

0.7500 Gm. was dissolved in 100 c.c. of ether and the following results were obtained.

	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	7th day.
P.c. of enol ...	89	92	95	97

(At Higher Concentration).

1.3176 Gms. in 100 c.c. of alcohol showed 80% of enol on the 1st day and 70% the next day.

Hydroxymethylene Camphor.

0.2478 Gm. of hydroxymethylene camphor in 100 c.c. of alcohol.

	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.
P.c. of enol...	98.4	92.85	87.12	81.75.

Hydroxymethyleneacetotoluene.

0.8435 Gm. of the substance dissolved in 100 c.c. of alcohol.

	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.
P.c. of enol...	96.2	79.6	61.5	60.8	42.7

Hydroxymethylene-3:4-methylcyclohexanone.

(In Alcohol).

1.0146 Gms. of the substance were dissolved in 100 c.c. of alcohol.

1st day	78%
After a month	40%
On boiling with alcohol	52% (first day)

(In Benzene).

0.3156 Gm. was dissolved in 250 c.c. of benzene.

	1st day.	2nd day.	After a month.
P.c. of enol ...	82	86	86

1.8 Gms. in 100 c.c. of benzene gave 75% of enol in freshly prepared solution.

(In Ether).

0.6081 Gm. was dissolved in 250 c.c. of ether and the following results were obtained

	1st day.	2nd day.	After a month.
P.c. of enol ...	88	89	87

(In *cycloHexane*).

0.58 Gm. was dissolved in 75 c.c. of *cyclohexane*; 81% of enol was found in freshly prepared solution.

Hydroxymethylene-o-methylcyclohexanone.

Percentage of enol = 46.

The laboratory temperature during these experiments was on an average 27°.

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